

A Moderated Mediation Model of the Relationship between SMEs' Resources and their Sustainable growth, Lao PDR

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Received: May 26, 2025

Accepted: Jun 25, 2025

Published: Jun 28, 2025

Abstract

Purpose: This paper aims to determine the Government support (GSM) and Private support (PSM) act as moderators in the relationship between SMEs' resources: Financial resources (FRR), financial literacy (FLR), Managerial capacities (MCR) and Market orientation (MKR) and their technological innovation awareness (TIA); and to discover the GSM and PSM modify the indirect relationship between SMEs' Resources and their Sustainable growth (SG) through TIA, making the indirect relationship stronger at higher of both supports.

Design/Methodology: Using the survey method and adopted a random sampling technique. Data was collected with 517 SME' owners/managers, engaged in the business commodity production, trade and services. Structural Equation Modelling, Interaction effects, and The PROCESS Model 7 were performed to test the proposed hypotheses by using SPSS/AMOS version 23.

Finding: Results confirmed 13 out of 24 hypotheses: Relationships between resources (FLR, MCR, MKR) and TIA were moderated by GSM, while the impact of FLR and MCR on TIA was regulated by PSM. Moderated Mediation effect shown the indirect relationships between SMEs' resources (FLR, MCR, and MKR) and their FSGE and NFSGE through TIA were moderated by GSM. Furthermore, PSM modify the effect of FLR on FSGE and NFSGE via TIA. Level of GSM and PSM increased, TIA tended to rise with positive associated with FSGE and NFSGE, consequently, these indirect relationships were higher at elevated levels of both supports.

Implication: Evidence supports existing theories, informs the importance of businesses' resources and TIA used in enhancing business performance, while also emphasizing the necessity for authorities, agencies, and partners to expand their supports through various interventions, programs, and initiatives aimed to empowering SMEs improve their resources and utilize TIA in their operations to achieve sustainable growth.

Keywords Resources of SMEs, Technological Innovation Awareness, Sustainable growth of SMEs, Government support, Private support.

Paper type: Research Paper

Introduction

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play an important role in driving sustainable economic growth, creating jobs, generating and distributing income, and enhancing productivity (WBG, 2019). They contribute to technological innovation and engage with various parties to support sustainable economic growth. Therefore, investing effectively in the SG of these businesses is very important and cannot be ignored. However, most of them still suffer from limited resource constraints and unsystematic business planning that often negatively impact growth, survival, and sustainability (Rahman et al., 2016). Survival of a firm depends on business performance, long-term growth strategies and ability to maintain competitive advantage and growth (Yoo et al., 2018). Businesses need to maintain their sustained growth to avoid financial issues (El Madbouly, 2022). Meanwhile, business SG is not a new concept, it refers to continuous steady growth, and in terms of financial dimensions, indicates the maximum rate of firm's sales without depleting financial resources (Ashta, 2008; Higgins, 2009; Prabawani, 2013). Therefore, SMEs face challenges in achieving and maintaining their SG, which is more than a chance because it actually exists. At the same time, Lao SMEs are similar to those in other countries. Because, they are crucial to the National Socio-Economic Development. For this reason, the government has developed policies to promote and support them by providing diversified sources of funds and strengthening other facilities. According to Decree No.25/GOL, dated 16th January 2017, they are defined as enterprises related to commodity production, Trade, and services with annual income and total assets not exceeding Lao Kip 06 billion and annual average labor of less than 99 people.

The interest in the resource-based view (RBV) of an organization's performance and growth has increased, which is a critical strategic perspective that was built on Penrose (1959), compose of resources and competence, which is the main theoretical perspectives in strategic management theory (Amit & Schoemaker, 2016). Previous studies found some factors of a firms' resources affect their business growth. For instance, Effect of entrepreneurs' abilities on SMEs' SG (Diabate, Sibiri, et al., 2019), personal factors, business characteristics, managerial factors, capital availability, business support, and business environment on SMEs' success (Al-Tit et al., 2019), management capacities, technology, marketing and innovation technical competency (Kim, 2021). In Laos, no research has been conducted on the government support and private support moderate the indirect relationships between SMEs' Resources and their SG through TIA. However, past studies found others evidence. For instance, Government and non-government could support SMEs to overcome their challenges with high taxation, high inflation, unstable

exchange rates, and fund limitations. They also didn't pay enough attention to innovation awareness, competitiveness abilities, and have market and network limitations (Kyophilavong, 2007). Entrepreneurial orientation positive impacted on competitive advantages, and then, they impacted on SMEs' growth (Sirivanh et al., 2014). Moreover, previously studies investigated only the relationship between an enterprises' resources and their businesses performance and growth. Therefore, this study attempts to fulfill the research gaps to prove the indirect relationship between SMEs' resources and their SG through TI with moderation of GSM and PSM due to the limitation dedicated to SMEs' SG in developing countries, for instance in Laos.

The study aims: (a) to find out the GSM and PSM moderate the relationship between SMEs' Resources and their TIA, such as these relations will be higher among SMEs with high GSM and PSM; and (b) to discover the indirect relationship between SMEs' Resources and their SG through TIA is moderated by GSM and PSM, such these indirect relationships are stronger at higher levels of GSM and PSM. To achieve the research objectives, this paper is structured: Overview of the relevant literature and hypotheses development that could provide theoretical features on which to look at the research. Then focuses on research method, findings, discussion, research implications and conclusion.

Literature review

Sustainable Growth of SMEs: the concept of SG firms is introduced to test the consistency of a firm's growth objectives with its financial policies including increasing annual percentage in sales and assets without issuing of new equity (Ashta, 2008; Higgins, 2009). Firm growth could become sustainable and unsustainable (Babcock, 1970), which means not just to survive but to maintain competitive within the industry (Fonseka et al., 2012).

Resource Based Theory (RBV) was developed through numerous publications from the 1980s to 1990s. Resource refers to tangible and intangible assets to conceive and implement business strategies (Barney, 1991; Barney et al., 2001; Porter, 1981; Wernerfelt, 1984), which consists of resources and capacities. Resources consist of financial or physical assets, know-how that can be traded (patents and licenses) and human capital. These resources are linked and converted into final products and services (Amit & Schoemaker, 2016). This paper applies theory by selecting some SMEs' resources that appropriate to the Lao context and thought to be likely contributed to business SG, including FRR, FLR, MCR, and MKR.

Financial resources (FRR): Business finance refers to firm's ability to access external finances and to allocate internal resources for maximizing the return on investment. Retained profits and household savings are internal funds (Myers & Majluf, 1984; Osei-Assibey, 2013). Profits and liquidity are capital management objectives (Pass & Lowes, 1978; Rahim, 2017). Earlier studies measured FRR by twelve items (Hossain, 2020; Roxas & Chadee, 2012) and found it influenced on financial performance (Khan et al., 2022), and indirectly influenced on firms' SG through their profitability (Nastiti et al., 2019).

Financial literacy (FLR) refers to the set of skills and knowledge necessary for effective decisions, use financial services, and business position in the market (Reich & Berman, 2015), consists of knowledge, attitude, and awareness dimensions (Eniola & Entebang, 2017). Previous studies measured FLR by twelve items (Yang et al., 2018; Ye & Kulathunga, 2019), and found it influenced on firms' sustainability (Ye & Kulathunga, 2019) and on firms' performance (Abdallah et al., 2024; Agyapong & Attram, 2019; Eniola & Entebang, 2017; Huston, 2010; Yakob et al., 2021).

Managerial capacities (MCR) plays an important role in accomplishing business goals by integrating resources through productive teamwork with additional knowledge and expertise (Hussain et al., 2020). RBV identifies resources and capabilities are the source of a firms' sustainable competitive advantages (Barney et al., 2001). An enterprise's knowledge, experience, and management abilities are critical to business success (Popescu et al., 2020). Previous studies measured MCR by nineteen items (Bourne & Franco-Santos, 2010), found It influenced on firms' SG (Hussain et al., 2020) and indirectly influenced on performance via organizational performance (Zack et al., 2009).

Market orientation (MKR) is the process by which a business gather market information pertinent relevant to the current and future needs of its customers and share it both internal and externally the organization (Kohli et al., 1993; Sen, 2006), consists of customer orientation, competitor orientation and inter-functional co-organization components (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990; Narver & Slater, 1990; Slater & Narver, 1994). Earlier studies measured MKR by twelve items (Narver & Slater, 1990), found it had effect on firm growth (Subramanian & Gopalakrishna, 2001) and firms' performance (Buli, 2017; Cano et al., 2004; Hoque & Awang, 2019).

Diffusion of innovation theory (DOI) according to Rogers (2003) refers to the "process by which innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social system" and an innovation is "an idea, practice, or object perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adoption". While technology is defined as "a design for instrumental action that reduces the uncertainty in the cause-effect relationships involved in achieving a desired outcome". Moreover, DOI theory has mainly focused on the perceived features of technology and the innovativeness of the organization adopting them.

Technological innovation awareness (TIA) is a mediating variable in this study that refers to ideas and knowledge of new goods, processes, and services that create commercially successful (Madrid-Guijarro et al., 2009; Zastempowski et al., 2020). Schumpeter (1934) defined "Innovation means the introduction of new techniques and organizational models for introducing of new things in industry: products, method of production, market opening, development of raw material sources or other inputs, and creation of new market structures" (Ince et al., 2016). Previous studies measured TIA by 6 items (Chege & Wang, 2020b), found it had impacted on business performance and organizational effectiveness (Yoo et al., 2018). Leadership styles and innovation influenced on sustainable performance (Hassan et al., 2021). It mediated relationship between management and firms' performance (Ruiz-

Palomo et al., 2019); and between strategic agility and firm performance (Yildiz & Aykanat, 2021).

Moreover, this study predicts a moderated mediation effect (Preacher et al., 2007). These relations suggest that the causal effect of TIA linking the SMEs' resources to increased SG among SMEs may be boost at higher levels of GS and PS. Therefore, Stakeholders' theory has been used as a ground theory.

Stakeholders' Theory introduced by R. E. Freeman, emphasizes the integration of business and ethnicity (Freeman, 1994), becomes popular in academically and professionally management literature due to its foundation of descriptive accuracy instrumental power and normative validity (Donaldson & Preston, 1995), and can be seen from the Barnett and Salomon (2012) who found businesses with high influence of stakeholders (CSP) demonstrate highest corporate financial performance (CFP). Two moderator variables:

Government Support to SMEs (GSM): Government plays a crucial role in creating the necessary enabling environment and relieving the burden of regulatory procedures for SMEs (Chowdhury, 2007), work together with other stakeholders by developing skills, sharing business information, building suitable networks, and etc. (Mahadea & Kabange, 2019). Adoption of sustainable technology is greatly aided by government policies and subsidies (Bakar et al., 2020). Previous studies found GSM moderated the relationships between financial literacy and fintech usage (Pranoto, 2024), market orientation and radical innovation (Cai et al., 2015), environmental context and TI adoption (Ngisau & Ibrahim, 2020), supply chain integration and SMEs' innovation performance (Chen et al., 2023), and between the use and adoption of technology and influenced SMEs' performance (Tang et al., 2024). SMEs' SG was impacted by tax incentives (Obafemi et al., 2021; Twesige & Gasheja, 2019). Government regulations, however, had negative impacted on sales revenue and performance. In contrast, knowing where to find funding greatly boosted sales revenue and profits, created jobs, etc. (Mahadea & Kabange, 2019), and SMEs' survival was impacted by financial government, but not their capacity to increase their yearly sales and assets (Park et al., 2020).

Private support to SMEs (PSM): Private sectors focus on supporting business growth (Hossain et al., 2020). They provide help for both financial and non-financial conditions and small firms require distinct information, financial strategies, government financing schemes, financial service items, etc. (Hossain, 2020). Previous studies found PSM moderated the relationships between finance, financial literacy, and financial and non-financial growth firms (Hossain, 2020), and Supporting institutions for developing SME technology innovation consist of government institutions, private institutions, financial institutions (banks) and nonbank financial institutions (Indrawati, 2020).

Hypothesis development

To address the study's objectives, 24 hypotheses were proposed, as follows:

Hypotheses Group 1: GSM and PSM moderate of the relationships between SMEs' Resources and TIA, such SMEs with high GSM and PSM will have a stronger relationship between SMEs' resources and TIA.

H₁₋₁: GSM moderates the relationship between FRR and TIA.

H₁₋₂: GSM moderates the relationship between FLR and TIA.

H₁₋₃: GSM moderates the relationship between MCR and TIA.

H₁₋₄: GSM moderates the relationships between MKR and TIA.

H₂₋₁: PSM moderates the relationship between FRR and TIA.

H₂₋₂: PSM moderates the relationship between FLR and TIA.

H₂₋₃: PSM moderates the relationship between MCR and TIA.

H₂₋₄: PSM moderates the relationships between MKR and TIA.

Hypotheses Group 2: GSM and PSM modify the indirect relationship between SMEs' Resources and SG through TIA, making the indirect relationship stronger at higher GSM and PSM levels.

H₃₋₁: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' FRR and FSFE through TIA.

H₃₋₂: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' FRR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₄₋₁: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between entrepreneurs' FLR and FSFE through TIA.

H₄₋₂: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between entrepreneurs' FLR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₅₋₁: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MCR and FSFE through TIA.

H₅₋₂: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MCR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₆₋₁: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MKR and FSFE through TIA.

H₆₋₂: GSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MKR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₇₋₁: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' FRR and FSFE through TIA.

H₇₋₂: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' FRR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₈₋₁: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between entrepreneurs' FLR and FSFE through TIA.

H₈₋₂: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between entrepreneurs' FLR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₉₋₁: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MCR and FSFE through TIA.

H₉₋₂: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MCR and NFSFE through TIA.

H₁₀₋₁: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MKR and FSFE through TIA.

H₁₀₋₂: PSM moderates the indirect relationship between SMEs' MKR and NFSFE through TIA.

Conceptual framework

Figure 1. Research framework

Methodology

Study design, Measures and measurements

This research was cross-sectional design and utilized a questionnaire instrument that was adapted from prior studies, and developed in the Lao language. Respondents were asked to answer the questions on a five-point Likert scale (from “strongly disagree” =1 to “strongly agree” =5).

To verify the liability and ensure validity of the questionnaire, it was adjusted based on three senior academics of Lao National University for the IOCs, followed by conducting field trials with SMEs’ entrepreneurs (owners/managers) before main study. Questionnaire composed: FRR, FLR, MCR, MKR, TIA, SG, GSM and PSM. All eight variables (nine constructs) were measured by various dimensions and 89 reflective items, and some items were then eliminated due to the reliability and validity tests.

Sampling and data collection

Target population was SMEs’ owners or managers whose owners were absent from business since they involve responsibility in business activities, and their businesses have been operating for at least three years to measure outcomes (Corić et al., 2011). Using random sampling technique from the listed SMEs of the 3rd National Economic Survey in 2019-2020, have experienced loans with any funding sources, their headquarters in the four main provinces: Vientiane Capital, Luangprabang, Savannakhet, and Champasack, because they account for more than 53 percent of SMEs overall country (LSB, 2020). Sample size was determined by the rule of thumb under the guidance of the requirements for data analysis techniques, which require 15-20 observations for each predictor (Hair et al., 2013). Data were collected between November 2022 to January 2023 with 523 respondents. Final sample were 517 due to the information completion.

Analytical strategy

Data was analyzed by using SPSS/Amos 23.0 to test hypotheses with multivariate analysis method. **First:** confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to assess uni-dimensionality, then the reliability and validity were assessed after model fit. **Second:** Structural equation modeling (SEM) techniques for testing the moderator role of GSM and PSM by interaction effect (Baron & Kenny, 1986). **Third:** The PROCESS Model 7 to test the moderated mediation model (Hayes Andrew, 2013). Here, five thousand samples set as bootstrapping were generated to study the indirect effect (conditional) of SMEs’ resources over SG through TI at diverse levels of GSM and PSM.

Results

Sample characteristics

Out of 517 total respondents, 82 percent were owners, 52.2 percent were male. Majority completed high school. They mostly run businesses in trade (44.1 percent). The average business operating period was 9.86 years (57.1 percent). Around three quarters (73.3 percent) had fewer than 5 employees and three-quarters (70 percent) of business funding were bank loans (Table 2, Appendix).

Descriptive statistic

Data was screened to check for inaccurate data entry, out-of-range values, missing and outliers, and tested the normality. Normality tests were confirmed by satisfactory and acceptable Skewness and Kurtosis below the cutoff value of +/-3 (Kline, 2011), a positive correlation of all items within latent constructs (Coltman et al., 2008), no threat of the constructs’ multicollinearity in this study due to the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value above 3 and lower value (below 0.2) of Tolerance (Hair et al., 2013), and no Systematic Measurement Errors because of the absence of the Common Method variance (CMV) by Harman’s single-factor test (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Assessment of Measurement Model

After ensuring the structural model free from CMV and collinearity issues. Measurement model analysis determined the factor loadings and fit indices illustrating the absolute fit level of CMIN/df=1.902 provided satisfactory value <2 (Schumacker & Lomax, 2004); GFI= 0.855; CFI=0.939; TLI=0.932; SRMR=0.040 and RMSEA=0.042, which show acceptable values (Bentler, 1990; Hu & Bentler, 1998) (Figure 2, Appendix). Then, Reliability and Validity of constructs were tested (Table 4, Appendix), which presents Cronbach's alpha values at greater than 0.7 and the Composite reliability values above 0.7. Construct validity, which presents the Standardized Factor Loadings of items provided satisfactory values above 0.5. Average Variance Extraction (AVE) found satisfactory values at greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2013). Final total items were 50 for all constructs. Then, Discriminant Validity was confirmed by assessing HTMT Ratio of Correlation, which displayed acceptable values below 0.8 (Henseler et al., 2014) (Table 5, Appendix). Therefore, Measurement model recognized sufficient evidence of construct validity and reliability.

Assessment of the Structural Model

Above CFA analysis was strongly supported continuing the structural model test by assessing path coefficients and P-values, which is a multivariate technique that combines the aspects of multiple regression and factor analysis to assess the interconnected relationship at once together (Fan et al., 2016; Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2013). Research used a 95% confidence interval (CI) to determine whether the hypotheses were supported or rejected. **First**, testing impact of moderators. **Second**, testing moderated mediation effect model.

Hypothesis testing

Moderation effect of GSM and PSM on the relationships between SMEs' Resources and their TIA.

Before testing the proposed relationships, the study's variables were mean-centered as Aiken et al. (1991) recommendations. Analyses accepted five among eight hypotheses when TIA was considered a dependent variable in a model (Table 6). **First**: Interaction term indicated significantly positive of GSM on the relationships between FLR, MCR and MKR, and TIA at (b = 0.123, P = 0.000), (b = 0.146, P=0.000) and (b = 0.108, P=0.000), respectively. Effect of FLR, MCR and MKR on TIA increase at higher GSM levels was reflected in the simple slope test. Buffering effect of GSM on the link between SMEs' FLR, MCR and MKR and their TIA was also evident in the moderation graph (Figure 3, 4 and 5, Appendix). **Second**: analyses also found significantly positive of PSM on the relationships between FLR and MCR, and their TIA at (b = 0.126, P=0.000) and (b = 0.078, P=0.021), respectively and the simple slope test reflects that FLR and MCR impacted on TIA boost at higher level of PSM in the moderation graph (Figure 6 and 7, Appendix). Therefore, for SMEs that receive a lot of government and Private helps, these beneficial relationships were strong. Results support hypothesis H₁₋₂, H₁₋₃, H₁₋₄, H₂₋₂ and H₂₋₃.

Table 6: Interaction effect results for moderation role of GSM and PSM

Hypothesis	Estimate	C.R.	P-value	Results	
TIA ← FRR*GSM	H ₁₋₁	-0.008	-0.214	0.831	Rejected
TIA ← FLR*GSM	H ₁₋₂	0.123	3.456	0.000	Supported
TIA ← MCR*GSM	H ₁₋₃	0.146	4.208	0.000	Supported
TIA ← MKR*GSM	H ₁₋₄	0.108	3.311	0.000	Supported
TIA ← FRR*PSM	H ₂₋₁	-0.024	0.704	0.481	Rejected
TIA ← FLR*PSM	H ₂₋₂	0.126	3.673	0.000	Supported
TIA ← MCR*PSM	H ₂₋₃	0.078	2.305	0.021	Supported
TIA ← MKR*PSM	H ₂₋₄	0.048	1.488	0.137	Rejected

Source: Author's calculation

Moderated Mediation effect of GSM and PSM.

Analysis found 6 from among hypotheses that the conditional indirect effect of SMEs' resources on their SG via TI at high and low values (\pm SD from mean) of GSM were significantly positive (Table 7).

First: Indirect effect of FLR on FSGE and NFSGE through TIA strengthened at a high level of GSM (+SD from means: effect= 0.130, 95%CI: [0.079; 0.185]; and effect= 0.146, 95%CI: [0.094; 0.207], respectively. However, they weakened at a low level of GSM (-1SD from the means: effect= 0.064, 95%CI: [0.025; 0.115] and effect= 0.073, 95%CI: [0.026; 0.132], respectively. To further verify whether the indirect effect is affected by GSM, data was tested whether the bootstrapped CI of the moderated mediation index contained zero. Results indicated that the moderated mediation effect were positive and had a non-zero probability (β =0.041; 95% bias-corrected CI: [0.014; 0.080]) and (β = 0.046; 95% bias-corrected CI: [0.017; 0.081]), respectively. Therefore, GSM moderated indirect effect of FLR on FSGE and NFSGE via TIA.

Second: Indirect effect of MCR on FSGE and NFSGE through TIA strengthened at a high level of GSM (+SD from means: effect= 0.165, 95%CI: [0.111; 0.232]; and effect= 0.180, 95%CI: [0.119; 0.248], respectively. However, weakened at a low level of GSM (-1SD from the means: effect= 0.081, 95%CI: [0.035; 0.145]; and effect= 0.088, 95%CI: [0.039; 0.156], respectively. Furthermore, results of bootstrapped CI of the moderated mediation index were positive and had a non-zero probability (β = 0.052; 95% bias-corrected CI: [0.020; 0.091]; and (β = 0.057; 95% bias-corrected CI: [0.021; 0.101]), respectively. Therefore, Indirect effect of MCR on FSGE and NFSGE via TIA was modified by GSM.

Third: Indirect effect of MKR on FSGE and NFSGE through TIA strengthened at a high level of GSM (+SD from means: effect= 0.229, 95%CI: [0.148; 0.325]; and effect=0.200, 95% CI: [0.125; 0.284], respectively. However, weakened at a low level of GSM (-1SD from the means: effect= 0.154, 95%CI: [0.098; 0.229]; and effect= 0.135, 95%CI: [0.082; 0.204], respectively. In addition, result of bootstrapped CI of the moderated mediation index was positive and had a non-zero probability (β =0.047; 95%bias-corrected CI: [0.010; 0.097]; and (β = 0.041; 95%bias-corrected CI: [0.008; 0.083]), respectively. Therefore, GSM moderated the indirect effect of MKR on FSGE and

NFSGE through TIA.

Moreover, the Johnson-Neyman technique recommended by Hayes (2018) was plotted the conditional indirect effect of FLR, MCR, and MKR on FSGE and NFSGE via TIA with its associated 95%CI based on the second-order variance (Preacher et al., 2007). Findings indicated the indirect effects were significant distinct from zero for all values of GSM (Figure 8-13). Hence, hypothesis $H_{4,1}$, $H_{4,1}$, $H_{5,1}$, $H_{5,1}$, $H_{6,1}$ and $H_{6,2}$ were supported.

Table 7: Conditional Indirect Effect of FLR on SG through TIA at diverse levels of GSM (N = 517, Bootstrapping = 5000 Samples).

1. Financial Literacy (FLR)	b	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
H_{4,1}: DV=FSGE					
FSGE ← TIA	0.257	0.035	0.000		
FSGE ← FLR	0.442	0.04	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
FSGE← TIA ← FLR	0.097	0.022	0.000	0.059	0.141
Conditional indirect effects of GSM	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
GSM low-0.802	0.064	0.023	0.001	0.025	0.115
GSM mean	0.097	0.022	0.000	0.059	0.144
GSM high +0.802	0.130	0.027	0.000	0.079	0.185
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.041	0.016	0.001	0.014	0.080
H_{4,2}: DV=NFSGE					
NFSGE ← TIA	0.283	0.046	0.000		
NFSGE ← FLR	0.285	0.045	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
NFSGE ← TIA← FLR	0.109	0.025	0.000	0.066	0.162
Conditional indirect effects of GSM	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
GSM low-0.802	0.073	0.027	0.002	0.026	0.132
GSM mean	0.109	0.025	0.000	0.066	0.162
GSM high +0.802	0.146	0.029	0.000	0.094	0.207
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.046	0.016	0.001	0.017	0.081
2. Managerial Capacities (MCR)					
H_{5,1}: DV=FSGE					
FSGE ← TIA	0.276	0.044	0.000		
FSGE ← MCR	0.370	0.044	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
FSGE ← TIA ← MCR	0.123	0.026	0.000	0.078	0.179
Conditional indirect effects of GSM	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
GSM low-0.802	0.081	0.028	0.000	0.035	0.145
GSM mean	0.123	0.026	0.000	0.078	0.179
GSM high +0.802	0.165	0.031	0.000	0.111	0.232
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.052	0.018	0.001	0.020	0.091
H_{5,2}: DV=NFSGE					
NFSGE ← TIA	0.295	0.048	0.000		
NFSGE ← MCA	0.240	0.048	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
NFSGE ← TIA ← MCR	0.134	0.027	0.000	0.087	0.192
Conditional indirect effects of GSM	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
GSM low-0.802	0.088	0.030	0.000	0.039	0.156
GSM mean	0.134	0.027	0.000	0.087	0.192
GSM high +0.802	0.180	0.032	0.000	0.119	0.248
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.057	0.020	0.001	0.021	0.101
3. Market Orientation (MKR)					
H_{6,1}: DV=FSGL					
FSGE← TIA	0.343	0.051	0.000		
FSGE ← MKR	0.194	0.050	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
FSGE ← TIA ← MKR	0.192	0.035	0.000	0.127	0.266
Conditional indirect effects of GSM	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
GSM low-0.802	0.154	0.033	0.000	0.098	0.229
GSM mean	0.192	0.035	0.000	0.127	0.266
GSM high +0.802	0.229	0.045	0.000	0.148	0.325
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.047	0.022	0.009	0.010	0.097
H_{6,2}: DV=NFSGL					
NFSGE ← TIA	0.292	0.053	0.000		
NFSGE ← MKR	0.199	0.053	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
NFSGE← TIA ← MKR	0.167	0.033	0.000	0.107	0.237
Conditional indirect effects of GSM	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
GSM low-0.802	0.135	0.031	0.000	0.082	0.204
GS mean	0.167	0.033	0.000	0.107	0.237
GSM high +0.802	0.200	0.041	0.001	0.125	0.284
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.041	0.019	0.000	0.008	0.083

Source: Author's calculation

In addition, analyses similarly show significantly positive for the indirect effect of FLR on FSGE and NFSGE through TIA strengthened at a high level of PSM (+SD from means: effect= 0.107, 95% CI: [0.063; 0.157] and effect: 0.120, 95% CI: [0.078; 0.173]), respectively. But weakened at a low level of PSM (-1SD from the means: effect= 0.041, 95%CI: [0.005; 0.086]) and effect= 0.046, 95%CI: [0.003; 0.099]), respectively. Data was tested whether the bootstrapped CI of the moderated mediation index contained zero for further verifying whether the indirect effect was affected by PSM. Results indicated the moderated mediation effect was positive and had a non-zero probability ($\beta = 0.038$, 95% bias-corrected CI: [0.014; 0.073]) and ($\beta = 0.043$; 95% bias-corrected CI: [0.019; 0.075]), respectively. Therefore, PSM moderated the indirect effect of FLR on FSGE and NFSGE via TIA (Table 8). The Johnson-Neyman technique plot (Hayes, 2018) shows the conditional indirect effect of FLR on FSGE and NFSGE via TI with its associated 95%CI based on the second-order variance (Preacher et al., 2007) indicated that the indirect effects were significant distinct from zero for all values of PSM (Figure 14-15, Appendix). Hence, hypothesis H_{8-1} and H_{8-2} were supported.

Table 8: Conditional Indirect Effect of FLL on SG through TI at diverse levels of PS (N = 517, Bootstrapping = 5000 Samples).

Financial Literacy (FLR)	b	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
H₈₋₁: DV=FSGE					
FSGE ← TIA	0.257	0.041	0.000		
FSGE ← FLR	0.442	0.040	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
FSGE ← TIA ← FLR	0.074	0.018	0.000		
Conditional indirect effects of PSM					
	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
PSM low-0.802	0.041	0.020	0.031	0.005	0.086
PSM mean	0.074	0.018	0.000	0.043	0.116
PSM high +0.802	0.107	0.023	0.000	0.063	0.157
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.038	0.015	0.001	0.014	0.073
H₈₋₂: DV=NFSGE					
NFSGE ← TIA	0.283	0.046	0.000		
NFSGE ← FLR	0.285	0.045	0.000		
Indirect effect model					
NFSGE ← FLR ← TIA	0.083	0.021	0.000		
Conditional indirect effects of PSM					
	Effect	SE	P	LBCI95%	UBCI95%
PSM low-0.802	0.046	0.025	0.038	0.003	0.099
PSM mean	0.083	0.021	0.000	0.048	0.129
PSM high +0.802	0.120	0.024	0.000	0.078	0.173
Index of moderated mediation TIA	0.043	0.014	0.001	0.019	0.075

Source: Author's calculation

Discussion

Moderation effect of GSM and PSM on the relationships between SMEs' Resources and TIA.

Results demonstrate evidence supporting five among eight hypotheses: Interaction term for FLR, MCR, MKR and GSM, and PSM had a positive impact on TIA (Table 6 and Figure 3 - 7): The FLR, MCR, and MKR on TIA were weaker when GSM levels were low, but these effects got stronger as GSM increased (Figure 3, 4 and 5). This was consistent with hypothesis H_{1-2} , H_{1-3} and H_{1-4} . Similarly, when PSM levels were low, the FLRL and MCR on TIA was weaker, but as PSM increased, this effect became stronger (Figure 6 and 7), which aligns with hypothesis H_{2-2} and H_{2-3} . These findings validated the Pranoto (2024) study's conclusions that GSM moderated the effect of financial literacy on MSMEs' usage of financial Technology, and the relationship between market orientation and radical innovation (Cai et al., 2015). However, Chen et al. (2023) discovered that management commitment affected SMEs' innovation performance. Additionally, GSM influenced on the connections between the environment context and the adoption of technological innovation (Ngisau & Ibrahim, 2020), between the use and adoption of technology in firms' businesses (Tang et al., 2024), and government and private organizations are among those that assist SMEs with technological innovation (Indrawati, 2020).

Moderated Mediation effect of GSM and PSM modified the indirect relationship between SMEs' Resources and SG through TIA.

Evidence supporting eight among sixteen hypotheses (Table 7-10 and Figure 8 - 15): GSM moderated the relationship between SMEs' resources, in this case, FLR, MCR, and MKR and their FSGE and NFSGE through TIA. According to the findings, TIA tend to grow and was positively correlated with FSGE and NFSGE as GSM levels rise. This supported hypotheses H_{4-1} , H_{5-1} , H_{6-1} , H_{4-2} , H_{5-2} and H_{6-2} . In addition, PSM moderated the relationship between SMEs' resources, in this case FLR and their FSGE and NFSGE through TIA. According to the findings, when PSM levels rise, TIA tend to increase and was positively correlated with FSGE and NFSGE. which offered proof to support hypotheses H_{8-1} and H_{8-2} . This result appears to conflict with the earlier research conducted in Bangladesh by Hossain et al. (2020) which discovered that government assistance had no moderating effect on the associations between finance, financial literacy, and business financial growth. Current finding, however, consists with earlier research by Hossain (2020) found the relationship between financial literacy and finance and non finance growth forms modified by Private support. Therefore, this research supports Stakeholder theory, which emphasizes the integration of business and ethnicity. As demonstrated by Barnett and Salomon (2012), who found that business with a high level of influence over stakeholders would have the best financial performance.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion, this study comes to the conclusion that, even though SMEs' owners and managers recognize the importance of their company's resources and capacities, doing so has benefits for attaining long-term company growth. Furthermore, the study demonstrated a consistency that presupposes SMEs will promote sustainable business success by valuing their business resources and capabilities through the application of technological innovation. Additionally, this study showed that government and private support modify the linkages between some SMEs' resources and technological innovation awareness. This indicated that as the level of GSM and PSM increased, TIA tended to rise with positives associated with their business sustainable growth. Consequently, these indirect relationships were higher at elevated levels of GSM and PSM, which examines the current entrepreneurial ecosystem in Lao PDR.

Implications of the study

This study has both practical and theoretical contributions. **First:** Providing the interrelation of an entrepreneur's perspective on sustainable business growth, this study makes the most significant contribution to the literature as well as supports the paradigm of SMEs' management. **Second:** Understanding the value of SMEs' resources in running their enterprises could help entrepreneurs increase productivity and achieve long-term success. These results demonstrate that the RBV is appropriate for explaining a firm's competency and physical resources. Consequently, business owners should make investments in both tangible and intangible resources. **Third:** Informing SME owners and managers increases the adoption of technology innovation and digital in business operations, in order to improve and attain sustainable business growth, which are the fundamental key indicators of business success during a turbulent competitive business environment. Because TIA makes available enterprise resources more efficient. **Fourth:** By providing information to authorities, agencies and other partners can learn how to increase support for various interventions, programs and/or initiatives that empower SMEs to adopt technology innovation and digital more widely in their operations and to help them manage their resources in both terms of tangible and intangible in a more effective manner, in order to achieve sustainable business growth.

Limitations of the study

This paper applied the cross-sectional study, in contrast to the longitudinal approach. It offers a better position to explore the causal relationship conclusion. Thus, the results of the current study may not be concluded as similar and consistent over time. In addition, the data was collected following the COVID-19 pandemic, when many companies cut employees. Meanwhile, this study sample frame was selected from the 3rd national economic survey 2019-2020 (pre-pandemic survey). Consequently, there are fewer SME employees than typical. Furthermore, results could not be compared across business sectors since the study sample was not equally distributed among them.

Recommendations

This paper only looks at the sustainable growth of SMEs; comparable studies on larger businesses and/or listed companies on the Lao Securities Exchange can be carried out due to the availability of their financial records, which allows for further data analysis testing. This allows us to analyze data in other ways, such as estimating the enterprise's sustainable growth rate (SGR), which should be considered as the dependent variable. Additionally, qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews with authorities and regulators and focus group discussions (FGD) among enterprises could be employed. Studying comparative techniques could be used to ascertain the degree of sustainable growth of various business sectors and to obtain a thorough comprehend of the elements required for sustainable business growth.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

APPENDIX

Table 2. Respondents and SMEs profiles.

Characteristics		Frequency (N=517)	Percentage
1. Respondents profile			
Position in business	Owner	424	82%
	Manager	93	18%
Gender	Male	273	52.8%
	Female	244	47.2%
Age of respondents (Years)	Means \pm SD:	43.5 \pm 9.77	
Level of Education	High school	282	54.5%
	Vocational education	64	12.4%
	Bachelor	154	29.8%
	Master	15	2.9%
	Ph.D.	2	0.4%
2. SME's Profile			
Age of business (Years)	Means \pm SD:	9.86 \pm 5.55	
Gender of entrepreneur	Male	295	57.1%
	Female	222	42.9%
Education of Entrepreneur	High school	280	54.2%
	Vocational education	68	13.2%
	Bachelor	151	29.2%
	Master	15	2.9%
	Ph.D.	3	0.6%
Type of business	Manufacturing	82	15.9%
	Trade	228	44.1%
	Service	207	40%
Size of business (Assets)	Small size	395	76.4%
	Medium size	122	23.6%
Number of employees (person)	Means \pm SD:	5.37 \pm 6.81	
	Less than 5	379	73.3%
	6-50	134	25.9%
	51-99	4	0.8%
Location of business	Urban	349	67.5%
	Rural has road	168	32.5%

Sources of funding (Each n=517).	Commercial bank	362	70%
	Financial institution	132	25.5%
	Government fund	16	3.1%
	Village fund	10	1.9%
	Others/ informal	40	7.7%

Table 4: Construct reliability and validity measures

Construct/Items	Factor loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability (CR)	AVE
	> 0.5	>0.7	> 0.7	> 0.7
Financial resource		0.765	0.59	0.81
	FR1	0.810		
	FR2	0.886		
	FR3	0.579		
Financial literacy		0.822	0.830	0.550
	FL1	0.778		
	FL2	0.723		
	FL3	0.684		
	FL4	0.760		
Managerial Capacities		0.883	0.870	0.500
	MC8	0.690		
	MC9	0.687		
	MC10	0.720		
	MC11	0.725		
	MC12	0.667		
	MC18	0.699		
	MC19	0.743		
Market orientation		0.842	0.840	0.510
	MK8	0.686		
	MK9	0.716		
	MK10	0.702		
	MK11	0.716		
	MK12	0.686		
Technology innovation awareness		0.878	0.890	0.580
	TI1	0.804		
	TI2	0.694		
	TI3	0.721		
	TI4	0.808		
	TI5	0.779		
	TI6	0.740		
Financial sustainable growth		0.846	0.890	0.660
	FSG1	0.740		
	FSG2	0.899		
	FSG3	0.895		
	FSG5	0.765		
Non-financial sustainable growth		0.821	0.83	0.620
	NFSG1	0.681		
	NFSG3	0.655		
	NFSG4	0.844		
Government Support		0.911	0.910	0.550
	GS1	0.572		
	GS2	0.713		
	GS3	0.781		
	GS4	0.800		
	GS5	0.730		
	GS6	0.762		
	GS7	0.785		
	GS8	0.759		
Private support		0.938	0.930	0.570
	PS1	0.774		
	PS2	0.828		
	PS3	0.710		
	PS4	0.792		
	PS5	0.731		

PS6	0.782
PS7	0.751
PS8	0.741
PS9	0.730
PS10	0.707

Table 5: Discriminant Validity using HTMT Ratio -

	FRR	FLR	MCR	TIA	MKR	FSGE	NFSGE	GSM	PSM
FRR									
FLR	0.497								
MCR	0.410	0.719							
TIA	0.478	0.560	0.602						
MKR	0.379	0.516	0.705	0.726					
FSGE	0.404	0.659	0.562	0.544	0.485				
NFSGE	0.166	0.496	0.452	0.466	0.453	0.587			
GSM	0.213	0.242	0.325	0.481	0.435	0.268	0.413		
PSM	0.266	0.517	0.456	0.585	0.517	0.511	0.435	0.674	

Moderating effect of GSM and PSM on the relationship between SMEs' Resources and their TIA.

Figure 3: Moderating effect of GSM on the relationship between the FLR and SMEs' TIA.

Figure 4: Moderating effect of GSM on the relationship between the MCR and SMEs' TIA.

Figure 5: Moderating effect of GSM on the relationship between the MKR and SMEs' TIA.

Figure 6: Moderating effect of PSM on the relationship between the FLR and SMEs' TIA.

Figure 7: Moderating effect of PSM on the relationship between the MCR and SMEs' TIA.

Conditional Indirect Effect of SMEs' Resources on their SG via TIA at high and low of GSM and PSM.

Figure 8: Conditional indirect effect of FLR on FSGE via TIA at high and low values of GSM.

Figure 9: Conditional indirect effect of FLR on NFSGE via TIA at high and low values of GSM.

Figure 10: Conditional indirect effect of MCR on FSGE via TIA at high and low values of GSM.

Figure 11: Conditional indirect effect of MCR on NFSGE via TIA at high and low values of GSM.

Figure 12: Conditional indirect effect of MKR on FSGE via TIA at high and low values of GSM.

Figure 13: Conditional indirect effect of MKR on NFSGE via TIA at high and low values of GSM.

Conditional Indirect Effect of SMEs' Resources on their SG via TI at high and low of PSM.

Figure 14: Conditional indirect effect of FLR on FSGE via TIA at high and low values of PSM.

Figure 15: Conditional indirect effect of FLR on NFSGE via TIA at high and low values of PSM.

Summary of final items for nine constructs.

1. Financial resource

- FR1-Start-up capital available
- FR2-Adequate financial resources/Satisfactory level with enterprise's finance
- FR3-be able to access/additional capital when necessary.

2. Financial literacy

- FL1-The ability to analyze firms 'financial performance periodically
- FL2-Firm prepares monthly income statement
- FL3-Firm Can compute the cost of loan capital
- FL4-Firm has savings account

3. Managerial Capacities

- MC8-Being effective communicators of business information
- MC9- Create collaborative behaviors within a team
- MC10- be able to persuade others
- MC11- have a combination of technical, cognitive, and interpersonal skills that enable them to effectively coordinate and organize their teams.
- MC12-well-participate within the organization and monitor business skills
- MC18-encourage the staff to take responsibility for the team's performance
- MC19-Interested in the long-term development and progress of our team member

4. Market orientation

- MK8-Business has a target to create the product competitiveness
- MK9- There is good coordination across the inside of our business
- MK10-Interparty, among sections/persons in our business shares information
- MK11-In our business, there is coordination between divisions in formulating a marketing strategy
- MK12-All parts in our business participate in the creation of added value for customers.

5. Technology innovation awareness

- TI1-Our business introduced a new line of products/services
- TI2-Our business invested in R&D new line of products/services
- TI3-Our business used new technology in the production/service process
- TI4-Our business used new methods/procedures in production and service delivery
- TI5-Our business has marketed new products/services
- TI6-Our business market share has increased due to the new branding of our product

6. Finance sustainable growth

- FSG1-Sales volume increased
- FSG2-Profit volume increased
- FSG3-Total assets increased
- FSG5-Ability to repay creditors

7. Non-financial sustainable growth

- NFSG1-Market share/size increased.
- NFSG3- Number of satisfactory customers increased.
- NFSG4-Reputation in public increased

8. Government Support

- GS1- Adequate infrastructure to run business as follows_ access to road, electricity, water, telephone, etc.
- GS2- License application and registration process
- GS3- Tax intensive for business.
- GS4- Favorable government policy.
- GS5- Maintain law and order situation.
- GS6- Skill training program organized by a government agency.
- GS7- Providing relevant information/knowledge that assists business.
- GS8- Creation of a local business environment that encourages business for growth/development.

9. Private support

- PS1- Providing information on the market.
- PS2- Information support on consumer of my products
- PS3- Providing information on capital source.
- PS4- Providing information on technologies to support my business.
- PS5- Provide information on raw material sources.
- PS6- Information support on government regulations that are relevant to my business.
- PS7- Training support to improve technical abilities.
- PS8- Training support to improve interpersonal abilities.
- PS9- Training support to help understand the business.
- PS10- Training support to enhance personal productivity.